

Mycena's trifles: phylogenomics, *Basidopus*, *Rufolamptera*, *Xuaniella* and some

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Text

Traditional taxonomy is way too arbitrary, but modern approaches give improvements. Focusing on monophyly and divergence times, the delimitation of taxonomic units has become more objective and balanced. For our ecology thesis, we have to classify and count fungal samples across various taxonomic ranks, a task that forced us to delve into groups we had not focused on recently. Some of these have not been updated for too long, with classification systems so imperfect that would damage our statistics if left unaddressed.

One such monster is the so-called genus *Mycena*. Given its enormous species diversity and long-standing polyphyly (Maas Geesteranus 1992; Bau *et al.* 2021), even after the suborder Mycenineae established (He *et al.* 2024), we could not confidently determine which genera truly belong to Mycenaceae until we examined it ourselves (Yang *et al.* 2025). Recent megaphylogeny show that wherever Mycenaceae goes, the boundary of *Mycena* stretches along (He *et al.* 2024; Vizzini *et al.* 2024). This “genus” is too vast and heterogeneous, with an ancestor diverged nearly 100 mya. Keeping it as a big one is out of date.

Funnier, other genera widely accepted in Mycenaceae (*e.g.*, *Cruentomyces*, *Favolaschia* & *Panellus*) actually cluster with the type species of *Mycena* in a poorly differentiated, assumed clade. This pattern, first suggested by ITS-based phylogenies (*e.g.*, Yang *et al.* 2025), is also strongly supported by the genome-scale phylogeny presented below (Figure 1). The studies by Ke *et al.* (2020) and Harder *et al.* (2024) are very important here for their significant contributions to the phylogenomic framework of Mycenaceae. Given all these, along with the fact that the resulting smaller genera are not morphologically featureless, there seems little reason to resist splitting *Mycena*. Attention please, *Rufolamptera* (resembling *Prunulus*) and *Basidopus* (similar to many taxa close to *Mycena* s. str.), which appear somewhat weak in macromorphology, receive strong support from this solid dataset as well.

▲ **Figure 1.** Phylogeny of Mycenaceae constructed with 668 full-length single-copy orthologous loci completely present in 87.50% sampled genomes by coalescent algorithm. Collections newly sequenced are highlighted in red.

Yet, despite what is just described, morphological evolution in macrofungi appears quite conservative OVER LARGER TIMESCALES. Even after millions of years of divergence, fundamental morphotypes may remain unchanged, leading to coarse delimitation at the level of genus, a relatively terminal practice in classification. Therefore, the future of macrofungal taxonomy may lean toward splitting where possible, except in cases like *Hymenagaricus-Heinemannomyces* where overly narrow “genera” are subject to be merged (Nawaz *et al.* 2024; Yang *et al.* 2024).

Convergent evolution is another classic example for the unreliability of morphology, and it certainly occurs in mycenoid fungi. *Rickenella* (Hymenochaetales), distantly related to most mycenoid lineages, was once classified under *Mycena* due to striking macro- and micromorphological similarities (Figure 2). At ultrastructural level, things become more weird as *Rickenella* challenges the presumed ancestral trait of Hymenochaetales by possessing perforated parentheses like true mycenoid fungi would do (van Driel *et al.* 2009).

▲ **Figure 2.** *Rickenella indica* found in Guangzhou City. Photos by Kun L. Yang.

Xuaniella urbica serves another lesson. It has often been misidentified as *Atheniella flavoalba*, or earlier as *Mycena flavoalba* (Yang *et al.* 2025). Due to the high morphological variability, *Xuaniella* can simulate these groups (Figure 3). However, a four-locus phylogenetic analysis reveals it to be a well-supported monotypic genus, with few genetic variation within its single species (Figure 4). Here again, irony strikes: *Leucoinocybe*, a genus somewhat distantly related to *Xuaniella*, includes species indistinguishable from the latter in some aspects (Figure 5).

▲ **Figure 3.** Variable morphology of *Xuaniella urbica*. Colors white via yellow via brown to even purplish black from top left to bottom right. Photos by Kun L. Yang.

▲ **Figure 4.** Four-locus concatenated (ITS-nrLSU-*rpb2-tef-1a*) phylogeny of *Xuanella* suggests only a single species with few internal genetic variation. Data already released in Yang *et al.* (2025).

▲ **Figure 5.** A second, brownish and larger species of *Xuanella*? Well it is actually a new species of *Leucoinocybe* that would soon be published (*L. danxiashanensis* Nom. ined.). Discovered near true *Xuanella*. Photos by Kun L. Yang.

New genomes analysed here will be released in later publications, and finally we present an ITS tree containing all "Mycena" species with relatively complete information available in GenBank (Figure 6). It highlights the striking genetic heterogeneity and ancient divergence within this assemblage. This matrix was difficult to align due to high variation, resulting in a tree with low resolution, so low that Mycenaceae as a whole lacks support. However, even in such a poor condition, the clades of *Basidopus* and *Rufolamptera* survive.

▲ Figure 6. ITS phylogeny of (nearly) all *Mycena* labeled species with such data available in GenBank. This dataset was hard to align due to the high variation among these samples, yet the genera and generic groups recognized in Yang *et al.* (2025) are still resolved, suggesting their robustness.

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